

THE EFFECT OF HIGH PRESSURE TORSION ON PARTICLE CLUSTERS IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH VERY FINE PARTICLES

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SUMMARY: An Al6061-10%SiC and an Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ powder metallurgy (PM) metal matrix composites (MMCs) with particle clusters are subjected to deformation by high pressure torsion (HPT) to different strains to improve the homogeneity of the particle distribution within the matrix. It is demonstrated that a declustering of the dense particle clusters during HPT is caused by a debonding of individual particles from the surface of the dense particle clusters whereas the diffuse particle clusters are deformed. Depending on the type of particle clusters, significant different strains are required to obtain a homogeneous particle distribution. A possibility of industrial application of HPT to fabricate specimens with a homogeneous particle distribution is discussed.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, high pressure torsion, particle clusters, declustering, homogeneous particle distribution.

INTRODUCTION

Inhomogeneous particle distribution in powder metallurgy (PM) metal matrix composites (MMCs) reinforced by small particles significantly degrades their ductility and formability [1, 2]. Standard secondary processing such as rolling and/or extrusion have been used so far to improve the homogeneity of the particle distribution in such MMCs, however, the application of these methods is restricted, since they lead to a decreasing thickness (or diameter) of the samples [2].

Recently, severe plastic deformation (SPD) has been proposed to solve the problem of the inhomogeneity of the particle distribution in PM MMCs [3, 4]. SPD methods induce very high strains into samples without a significant change of their shape [5]. The aim of this paper is to study the effect of the high pressure torsion (HPT) on particle clusters in MMCs.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials

An Al6061-10%SiC MMC and an Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC are used in this investigation. The SiC particle size is between 0.3 and 1 μm and the alumina particle size is between 1 and 5 μm. A few single particles with a size of about 10 μm can be observed in both materials. The composites were supplied in form of rods with a diameter of 25 mm. Both materials exhibit an inhomogeneous particle distribution in the as-fabricated condition (see Figs. 2a, 3a). The Al6061-10%SiC MMC contains mostly dense particle clusters (particle clusters without

Fig. 1: A schematical view of HPT specimen

matrix material between individual particles), see Fig. 2a. In the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC, a fraction of diffuse particle clusters (with some amount of matrix between individual particles) prevails; a few dense particle clusters are also observed (Fig. 3a).

High pressure torsion

Disks with a diameter of 8 mm and a thickness, $t = 0.8$ mm are cut perpendicular to the extrusion axis (Fig. 1). The specimens are subjected to HPT at a pressure of 5 GPa at room temperature. The number of turns n is selected to attain a certain equivalent strain at a radius r of 3 mm, according to the relation

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \frac{2\pi nr}{t\sqrt{3}}. \quad (1)$$

The specimens of the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC are deformed to equivalent strains of 1, 4, 16, 64, 256, and 512 at a radius of 3 mm. The Al6061-10%SiC specimens are deformed additionally to strains of 1024 and 2300.

Microstructural investigations

To study the microstructure of the MMCs after HPT, the deformed specimens are ground perpendicular to the shear plane (shaded plane in Fig. 1) and polished. The analysed plane is $r = 3$ mm apart from the torsion axis. The microstructure is studied by an optical microscope and a scanning electron microscope LEO 1525.

Only qualitative analysis of the particle distribution is performed for the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC. For the Al6061-10%SiC MMC, a detailed quantitative investigation of the effect of HPT on the dense particle clusters is performed: The evolution of the size and the shape of the dense particle clusters during HPT is studied by the computer program “analySIS”. The equivalent circle diameter (ECD) which is the diameter of a circle having the same area as the cluster, the aspect ratio, and the area of the dense particle clusters are estimated within the analysed area which has a size of 640 x 480 μm.

Fig. 2: The microstructure of the Al6061-10%SiC: a) in the as-fabricated condition; b) after HPT to a strain of 1; c, d) after HPT to a strain of 2300

RESULTS

Evolution of the particle distribution in the Al6061-10%SiC MMC

Fig. 2a illustrates the microstructure of the Al6061-10%SiC in the as-fabricated condition. The dense particle clusters have a size of up to 100 μm in the extrusion direction (parallel to the disk axis) and up to 50 μm in the transverse direction. Such large dense particle clusters consists of over 4 millions small SiC particles. Totally, 328 particle clusters are detected in the investigated area (Fig. 2a, Tab. 1). The average ECD-value equals 15.1 μm (Tab. 1). HPT to a strain of 1 results in a rotation of the particle clusters (Fig. 2b). Some of the dense particle clusters have divided into several smaller dense particle clusters and the number of particle clusters in the investigated area increases to 410 (Tab. 1). After HPT to a strain of 4, the number of dense particle clusters increases to 421. Declustering of the dense particle clusters starts by cluster erosion: The SiC particles are debonded from the particle cluster surfaces and move into the particle free matrix (Fig. 2d).

The number of detected particle clusters and the average ECD-value decrease with further increasing deformation (Tab. 1). After HPT to a strain of 2300, a rather homogeneous particle

Table 1: Number of particle clusters and their average ECD-value in the Al6061-10%SiC MMC in the as-fabricated condition and after HPT

Equivalent strain, ϵ_{eq}	0	1	4	16	64	256	1024	2300
Number of particle clusters	328	410	421	402	405	303	233	56
Average ECD-value [μm]	15.1	12.5	12.4	11.5	9.7	9.0	8.1	7.7

distribution is observed. Only 56 dense particle clusters still remain visible in the investigated area (Tab. 1, Fig. 2c): The number of dense particle clusters decrease with a factor of 6 in comparison to the as-fabricated condition. The average ECD-value of the dense particle clusters decreases to 7.7 μm (Tab. 1). The ratio of the total surface of particle clusters “dissoluted” in the matrix to the total surface of particle clusters in the as-fabricated condition, $A_{deb}^{cl}/A_{init}^{cl}$, increases to 97% (Fig. 3).

The histograms of the aspect ratio distribution (of the dense particle clusters) do not change significantly with increasing deformation: There is no plastic deformation of the dense particle clusters during HPT (Fig. 4). It should be also noted that no particle fracture is observed during HPT. Even a few large particles (with a size $>10 \mu\text{m}$) remained unbroken after a deformation strain $\epsilon_{eq} = 2300$. These particles are marked by circles in Fig. 2c.

Fig. 3: The ratio of total surface of debonded SiC particles from particle clusters to the total surface of particle clusters in the as-fabricated condition, $A_{deb}^{cl}/A_{init}^{cl}$, plotted vs. equivalent strain for the Al6061-10%SiC

Fig. 4: Histograms of the aspect ratio distribution in the Al6061-10%SiC PM MMC after HPT to a strain of: a) 4, b) 64, c) 256, d) 2300

The effect of HPT on the homogeneity of the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC

Fig. 5 illustrates the evolution of the microstructure in the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC during HPT. In the as-fabricated condition, the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC has a very inhomogeneous particle distribution (Fig. 5a). Large particle free zones with a size of up to 200 μm in the extrusion direction (parallel to the disk axis) and up to 40 μm in the transverse direction, are observed (Fig. 5a). The diffuse and dense particle clusters have a size of up to 40 μm in the direction perpendicular to the extrusion direction. HPT to a strain of 1 leads to a rotation of particle clusters and particles free zones (Fig. 5b). A significant improvement of the particle distribution is observed with further increasing deformation. After HPT to a strain of 16, the particle distribution is relatively homogeneous: No diffuse particle clusters are visible, there are only a few dense particle clusters. Some of them are marked by white arrows in Fig. 5c. The dissolution of the dense particle clusters proceeds very slowly. Similar to the Al6061-10%SiC MMC, it occurs by cluster erosion mechanism. The alumina particles are debonded from the particle cluster surface and move into the particle free matrix (Fig. 5d). A HPT to a strain of 512 is required to achieve a full erosion of the dense particle clusters in the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC (Fig. 5e). A few black spots in Fig. 5e are unbroken large alumina particles.

Fig. 5: The microstructure of the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃: a) in the as-fabricated condition; b) after HPT to a strain of 1; c) after HPT to a strain of 16; d) after HPT to a strain of 256; e) after HPT to a strain of 512

DISCUSSION

Declustering in MMCs during standard secondary processing and HPT

The results of this investigation show that the process of declustering in MMCs with dense particle clusters during HPT differs from that one during standard secondary processing

Fig. 6: Schematical presentation of the declustering process and the final microstructure in a MMC with dense particle clusters during: a) standard secondary processing, b) HPT

(extrusion and/or rolling). As was demonstrated in [1, 2], the particle clusters are elongated in the direction of extrusion and/or rolling (Fig. 6a). The mechanism of their elongation has not been clear so far. This can occur either by “plastic deformation” of the dense particle clusters or by erosion of individual particles from the top and bottom surface of clusters by the flowing matrix and their further movement to behind of the cluster (Fig. 7a). Anyway, the standard secondary processing leads very often to the presence of “particle rich bands” which still degrades the formability of the MMCs (Fig. 6a) [1]. In the case of HPT, however, there is no elongation of the dense particle clusters as the histograms of their aspect ratio distribution do not change even after very high strains (Fig. 4). Therefore, the declustering occurs by the debonding of the individual particles from the whole surface of the dense particle clusters and their further dissolution within the matrix (Fig. 7b). Therefore, no particle rich bands appear in the microstructure after HPT and a very homogeneous particle distribution is observed (Figs. 2e, 6b).

It should be noted that the behavior of the diffuse particle clusters during standard secondary processing and HPT seems to be similar. The diffuse particle clusters seem to be deformed plastically during HPT: In the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC, they disappear already after HPT to a strain of $\epsilon_{eq} \leq 16$ (Fig. 3c).

About industrial application of HPT to homogenize MMCs

This work clearly demonstrates that HPT can be successfully applied to produce specimens of MMCs with a homogeneous particle distribution. A shortcoming of HPT regarding commercialization is the relatively small size of the fabricated samples. Their diameter is limited by the maximum available pressure of a press. From our experience, to avoid the slip of specimens in the HPT device during deformation, the load applied to our specimens should not be less than 25 ton. An application of higher loads allows the fabrication of larger specimens. Nevertheless, in the cases, where the element sizes are very small, even small specimens processed by HPT might be important. It should be also noted that larger samples can be fabricated by other methods of severe plastic deformation [5].

Fig. 7: a) A possible model to explain the elongation of a dense particle cluster during rolling (extrusion); b) Declustering of a dense particle cluster during HPT

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of high pressure torsion (HPT) on the dense and diffuse particle clusters has been investigated in the Al6061-10%SiC MMC and the Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ MMC. It has been found that:

1. The diffuse and dense particle clusters behave different during HPT.
2. The diffuse particle clusters are plastically deformed.
3. The declustering of the dense particle clusters occurs by a mechanism of particle debonding from the surface of particle clusters without deformation of particle clusters. This process is different from the declustering during the standard secondary processing (extrusion or/and rolling) where dense particle clusters are “deformed”.
4. HPT can be successfully applied to fabricate relatively small disks of MMCs with a very homogeneous particle distribution.

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